

Method for producing 3D silicate based bioactive glass-ceramic scaffolds using digital light processing

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ABSTRACT

In the field of bone tissue engineering, silicate based bioactive ceramics have been extensively studied due to their bone-like apatite-formation ability when implanted into bone [1]. Recently, there is an increasing interest in highly porous scaffolds, seeking for effective osteoconduction, which mainly depends on the total porosity of the scaffolds, pore size and interconnected pore distribution that allows cellular migration, diffusion of nutrients and metabolites and the proper angiogenesis [2].

Advancements in additive manufacturing (AM) of bioactive materials enable complex porous geometries and net or near-net shape products to be fabricated to high accuracy without tooling such as moulds. Digital light processing is a lithography based technology that requires a photo-curable organic or inorganic resin (it has the special property of being able to become solid once it is exposed to light) as a matrix. Photo-curable silicone resin not only gives the final product shape, but also it yields ceramic/glass component known also as polymer derived ceramics (PDCs). By heat treatment it converts to SiOC or/and SiC in inert and to SiO₂ in ambient atmosphere [3]. Although some photo-curable silicones are already commercially available, the low ceramic yield (causing cracks and uncontrolled volume shrinkage), high costs and processability (require heavy metal traces containing photo catalytic initiator which, that would affect the biological activity) are critical parameters and need to be improved.

It has been reported that mixing of silicone resins with reactive oxide fillers after suitable thermal treatment yields silicate based bioceramics. Åkermanite (Ca₂MgSi₂O₇) 3D scaffolds with hierarchical porosity, i.e. macroporosity resulting from the applied AM technology and nanoscale pores resulting from the processing route) were prepared by direct ink writing of silicone resin mixed with CaCO₃ and MgO/Mg(OH)₂, after heat treatment at 1100°C. The achievement of phase purity is enhanced by the introduction of borate salts, providing liquid phase upon firing and promoting ionic interdiffusion [4].

The present study describes the method to produce 3D printed SiOC and Åkermanite porous scaffolds with complex shapes by digital light processing of a photocurable slurry consisting of engineered silicone mixtures. Considering the difficulties of using photocurable silicones, simple blending of commercial photo insensitive silicones with a sacrificial photocurable organic resin was applied as an alternative. Three commercial silicone resins (namely MK, H44 and H62C from Wacker Chemie AG) were selected and tested in order to ensure stable photocurable blends. The blends were further refined with the introduction of fillers (CaCO₃ and MgO/Mg(OH)₂), followed by firing at 1100 °C, in air to obtain complex shaped Åkermanite scaffolds. Optimized samples (from H44 resin) and reactive fillers (including up to 4.5wt% borax additive), led to crack-free, phase-pure scaffolds, with microporous struts.

Keywords: biomaterials; silicones; digital light processing; additive manufacturing; Åkermanite.

Fig.1 Optical and SEM images (cubic (a,b,c) and diamond (d,e,f) models) of H44 derived Åkermanite scaffolds

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